

Kidnapping and Socio-Economic Development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria- A Quasi-Social Analysis.

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ABSTRACT

Kidnapping has undoubtedly become a growing, lucrative, and preferable alternative to other types of crime. The gravity of kidnapping has become so intense that it has virtually affected all parts of contemporary Nigerian society. This article investigates kidnapping and the

socioeconomic development of the Niger Delta region. The study population is 400 respondents drawn from nine (9) states in the Niger Delta, comprising adult respondents aged 18 to 70 in six selected states of the Niger Delta. The article revealed that kidnapping initially began as a social crusade aimed at emancipating the Niger Delta region and raising awareness of its long-standing neglect, impoverishment, and underdevelopment to the international community. Nowadays, people are kidnapped on a daily basis for various reasons, such as economic, political, and personal differences. Some of the victims are killed or maimed. The article calls for the government at various levels to intensify awareness campaigns on the evils as well as punishment for kidnapping. Additionally, the enabling laws on kidnapping should be increased. The punishment for kidnapping should be as grave as that for murder and other felonious offences to further instill fear in would-be kidnappers. Finally, citizens should be encouraged to report any suspected incidence or kidnap attempt to security agencies without delay. On the other hand, more security personnel should be deployed to the various communities in the Niger Delta with better arms.

Keywords: Kidnapping, Social problem, Niger delta, Government, Policing style

INTRODUCTION

The crime of kidnapping has in recent times become endemic in the Niger delta. It has undoubtedly become a growing, lucrative, and preferable alternative to other types of crime. The gravity of kidnapping has become so intense that it has virtually affected all part of the contemporary Nigeria society.

Hardly a day passes in Nigeria without kidnapping incidents making the headlines in our villages, communities, towns and the social media. Kidnapping is an alien culture in Nigeria society. During pre-colonial and post-colonialism, and immediately after the Nigerian civil war, crimes that existed in Nigeria were burglary, theft, armed robbery, incest and rape. The perpetrators of these crimes were few by then and operated on the dark with utmost secrecy. The operations then did not pose many traits to the stability and security of Nigeria nation.

The current dimension of kidnapping became alarming in the Niger Delta region when militants in February 2006, abducted few oil workers, ostensibly to draw global attention to the dire situation in the oil- rich region of the country. The victims were mostly foreigners. Since then, the menace has so far gained popularity in other parts of the country, especially in the Northern part of the country. Now, their targets are no longer foreigners alone; but practically every Nigerian is a potential target. The group called itself “Enough is Enough” in the Niger Delta claimed responsibility.

Initially, this started as a social crusade for the emancipation of the Niger Delta region, and to create awareness of aged-long neglect, impoverishment and the underdevelopment of Niger Delta region to the international Community. Now People are kidnapped on daily basis for various reasons such as economic, political and personal differences. Some of the victims are

killed or maimed before they are rescued, while others are rescued by their relatives after paying ransom.

Data from 2015 to 2023 global kidnap index by the online tourism site revealed that Nigeria was placed second among the countries with high kidnapping rates. This rating puts Nigeria among countries with serious kidnapping problems. They include: Philippines, Venezuela, Columbia, Brazil, and Mexico (Ujumadu, 20018; Ekpe, 2020). Such report could serve as an assumption due to lack of accurate statistical data. Also, it has been reported that Nigeria as at August 2021, recorded 5612 cases of kidnapping and close to 3000 dead persons in kidnappers' den as against 4508 cases recorded throughout 2023 (Ekpe, 2023). The former inspector General of police in Nigeria stated that kidnappers and hostage-taker got N100 billion naira in ransom (about N900 billion naira) between 2015to 2023 (Kyrian, 2023). Kidnapping cases in Niger delta have been ravaging daily activities. The safety of persons in Nigeria and their property cannot be guaranteed. Kidnapping is an offence punishable by the law in Nigeria. Anybody got involved in the act is expected to face a penalty of 10years imprisonment. Apart from this, some states like Rivers, Abia, Akwa Ibom, Imo, and Delta, Bayelsa, have passed into law a bill termed "prohibition of hostage-taking and related offences law", with death penalty as punishment for offenders; (Inyang, 2015; Ekpe,2016).

But with the surge of kidnapping incidence in the state orchestrated by the ineffectiveness of security agents particularly the Nigerian Police, social insecurity and an increase of various forms of crimes, peoples' safety can longer be guaranteed, nightlife now becomes a bizarre to the people, particularly visitors in the State; business activities also suffers set back as people are afraid of being kidnapped, which led to the reduction in the workforce of some of these industries.

Statement of the Problem

Most Nigerians would agree that crime rates and insecurity in the country have become a source of concern over the years as the country has continued to experience steep rise in crime. Davidson (2020) points out that the general state of insecurity in some parts of the country has no doubt reached a stage where virtually everybody is now worried on the direction it is going. Presently, hardly can people sleep because of the fear of being robbed or kidnapped. Businessmen have taken flight with their businesses for fear of being kidnapped or robbed There are various organized and non-organized crime, such as smuggling of contrabands, especially firearms, counterfeiting, money-laundering, armed robberies, kidnapping, car hijacking, and human trafficking have become sources of worry for the Nigerian government. Likewise, incidents of high-profile crime and politically motivated killings and kidnapping have lately compounded the complexity of the crime situation in the country. Kidnapping is all over Nigeria and the criminal commerce of Kidnapping paints an ugly picture of the already battered image of

Nigeria and become a life-threatening ailment. For instance, there is no month in Nigeria when we do not read on the pages of newspapers about cases of kidnapping of young and old people. There are evidences that, the Niger Delta has lost hope of tomorrow because those who are involved in this ugly business find it difficult to quit because they see it as a business that can never be abolished by any government in Nigeria, in the sense that government of the day is yet to take a bold step to find a lasting panacea to this barbaric act. Onovo (2020) point to an interesting fact when he stated that the one of the barriers that reduces the capacity of governmental agencies to share criminal intelligence negates the fight against crime such as kidnapping. And that the Lack of a national process for generating and sharing intelligence, as well as the Existence of laws that unduly restrict law enforcement access to information, the hierarchical structures of sharing information, Deficits in criminal intelligence analysis. Lack of good technologies to support criminal intelligence sharing are major snag to the fight against kidnapping.

According to Brown, (2019). In his view expressed the fact that all efforts made in several spheres to address this problem have been greeted with little success and the tide has not really been stemmed. Itam (2020) records that governments, in reaction, have set up various anti-kidnapping squads across the country, better equipped with operational facilities to clamp down on kidnapping gangs, and more funds have been pumped into these agencies for maintenance and enhancement of their functioning, but the crime has continued seemingly unabated. In recent time, security enjoys the largest percentage of the budget with over Two billion eight hundred thousand Dollars (2.8\$) in the 2023 budget (Nasir Ahmed, 2023). Despite this huge budgetary allocation, the issue of kidnapping has continued to be on the increase. In the light of the above scenarios, that this study intends to look at kidnapping and its implication on the Socio-Economic Development of the Niger Delta.

Objectives of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to determine whether kidnapping, can impact socio Economic Development of the Niger delta.

While the specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Ascertain the root causes of kidnapping in the Niger delta .
2. Examine the nature of kidnapping as a crime in the Niger delta.
3. Ascertain the possible causes of the rise in the rate of kidnapping in Niger delta.
4. Examine the consequences on the socio-economic life of the niger delta.
5. Explore other ways which would complement the ability of the police in the fight against kidnapping in the niger delta.

Scope of Study

The study focuses on “Effect of kidnapping on the Socio-Economic Development in Niger delta. This implies that, the research work was conducted within and around the Niger delta.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the anomie/strain theory which attempts to provide the prospective on discrepancies between societal stated goals and the institutionalized means of achieving such goal. Robert K. Merton observed that there is a major contradiction between cultural goals and social structures. He calls this contradiction “Anomie” a concept first introduced by Durkheim. Robert K. Merton’s argument posits that cultural goal of achieving wealth is deemed possible for all citizens even though the social structure limits the legitimate “Institutionalized means” available for obtaining the goals. For Merton, legitimate institutionalized means are the protestant work ethics (hard work, education, deferred gratification). Illegitimate means are force and fraud. Because the social structure effectively limits the availability of legitimate institutionalized means, a strain is placed on people. Soyornbo (2016). Believes that it occurs “where there is an acute disjunction between the cultural norms and goals and the socially structured capabilities of members of the group to act in accord with them” In short, strain theory posits that the cultural values and social structures of society put pressure on individual citizens to commit crime. Merton believes that this strain will affect member of the lower class, in this regard therefore, the basic assumptions of the lower class envelopment at a higher level could be seen in the study area as indicated from our findings that unemployment, unequal distribution of natural resource, nature and character of the state has prepared reserved army of youths for recruitment in kidnapping and other crime related incidences. Thus, stalling socio-economic development in Niger delta. Drawing from Jock young on Merton’s anomie/strain theory, in his recent book, the exclusive society (2020), which he located crime in relation to both structural and cultural processes. Stating that structurally speaking, young argues that the dismantling of the welfare state, alongside increasing disparities between the rich and the poor, have served to further exclude disadvantaged groups. This theory explains the social problem of kidnapping in Niger delta, and its implications on the socio-economic development, the above argument of Metron’s theory reveals the menace. This is because, many Nigerians are unemployed and are living below the poverty line of two dollar a day, they invariably innovate their own means (kidnapping) which is not in line with the societal set goals to make a living. This implies that, if there are no jobs for the teeming population of graduates, and a good take home package for salary earners, kidnapping will always be a lucrative alternative venture to make a living alongside other crimes. The Anomie theory has is justified for adding an important dimension to our understanding that kidnapping is as a result of the strain between the societal set goals.

Experience of kidnapping in the Niger delta

In **Akwa Ibom state**, particular in uyo capital city the list of these been kidnapped keep increasing, the Akwa Ibom State Police Command on the 5th of July 2024 arrested four suspected kidnappers after a distress call which gave notification of a kidnap incident at Utang Street by Gibbs Street, Uyo. The Command's Anti-Robbery Squad, according to the police authorities, immediately swung into action and mobilized to the scene where four male suspects, Abdulkarem Yusuf, Yusuf Waziri, Inbinabo Sunny Iboroma and Abdulrahman Abbas were arrested. Preliminary investigations revealed that the suspects had earlier kidnapped one Abraham Ekpe at Ring Road 3, Opposite Cemetery. The gang members were arrested while they were on the verge of kidnapping one "Richie", the friend of their victim (Abraham Ekpe). Their plan was to take them to the Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State. The Police Public Relations Officer, ASP Timfon John confirmed that the kidnap suspects had demanded a ransom of five million naira from their victim, but he could not pay, prompting them to also kidnap his friend. The victims were all rescued successfully and have been reunited with their families. One red color Honda Accord car with registration number BJ 615 ABC, one handcuff, one dagger was recovered. The suspects will be charged to court upon completion of investigation.

Mr. Owen Owen, an expatriate oil worker with Exxon Mobil was kidnapped in a church premises close to his Mobil quarter horn in Eket. He was released after paying some ransom. Men of God and their children are not spared as some criminals on November 24, 2008 trailed one Evangelist Ita Enyong while on his way to church and kidnapped him. The daughter of a prominent preacher in Uyo, Abel Darnina, was also a victim. The list grew to include Mrs. Comfort Aloysius Etok, wife of a formal senator politician in Akwa Ibom State, who was kidnapped on Thursday, October 16, 2008. Others include: a Lebanese working with STEMCO, Sasive Khali and Hon. Nse Ntuen, the Chairman of ALGON – Formal Association of Local Government Council of Nigeria (David, 2019; Nsoh, 2019). Also, one Mr. Ikpe of Uruan Local Government Area was kidnapped and until today, he is nowhere to be found. His incidence left people to argue that he has been sent to his grave by his abductors (Micheal, 2020).

On June 14, 2019, the father of the former speaker, Akwa Ibom House of Assembly, Chief Nelson Effiong was kidnapped and killed after ransom payment had been made. Mr. Ubong Obot (Obotex) was also reported kidnapped and his barber who came to give him hair cut at his residence was killed in the process (David, 2019; Inyang, 2019). In June 30, 2020; a businessman, Engineer, Emmanuel Okon Ekpeyong and his younger sibling, Mathias, were killed in a foiled kidnap attempt. According to Inyang. (2020), the younger Ekpeyong was shot dead by an unknown kidnapping gang after pitting up a brave resistance against the abduction of his brother who was then bundled into the booth of an Audi 80 car. However, the bravado of Engineer Ekpeyong who forced the booth open tried to escape while the car was in motion proved to be in vain as he was brought down by the kidnapper's bullets.

A two-year-old boy, Master Favour Felix Effiong was reported kidnapped by people suspected to be ritualist. The boy according to family sources was kidnapped at about 10pm, on Wednesday, September 23 2019, on his way from church program with his mother. Also, Deaconess Ema Eshiet, mother of Mrs. Iniobong Eshiet, a former member of the Akwa Ibom State House of Assembly, was reported kidnapped in her house in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, on Wednesday, November 4, 2019. Information holds that the woman was released upon the payment of ten million Naira in somewhere in Port Harcourt City.

One Samuel Ita Imekong, a student of the University of Uyo was reported kidnapped by an identified hoodlums on November 25, 2019. One million naira was demanded for his release (Anonymous, 2019; Shield Newspaper, December, 9). Also, on December 4, 2020, the Bank Manager of United Bank of Africa (UBA) was abducted in front of his house along Nelson Mandela road, in the evening. An undisclosed millions of naira according to source was paid (Akpan, 2020).

Bayelsa State: On February 2006, militants in the Niger Delta first abducted a few oil workers, ostensibly to draw global attention to their dire situation in the oil-rich Niger Delta area of the country and the victims were mostly foreigners (Ekpe, 2009). Dode (2007) note that this first incident was carried out by the youths of Kou Kingdom in Bilabiri community, in the Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. The victims comprised Britons, Canadians and Americans, whose names were given as Texas Richards, Phil Morris, Au Wallace, Paul Sheppard, and John Steward, Lan Metocolf and peter Verrnulen. Still in Bayelsa State. On the 12th of January 2024 Bayelsa State Police Command have arrested four suspects allegedly involved in the kidnap of a 40-year-old businesswoman in the state, (Inyang 2019).

Confirming the arrest, the Commissioner of Police, Alonyenu Idu, said the victim was abducted at Opolo community in the Yenagoa Local Government Area. He said the four suspects included the wife of the alleged mastermind of the lady's abduction.

He also linked the youth unrest in Biogbolo-Epie in the same Yenagoa LGA to the disorderly conduct of some suspects believed to be involved in the kidnap of the businesswoman.

on March 4, 2009, unknown gunmen abducted a Lebanese worker known as David in the hitherto safe koluma Okpokuma Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. David is a member of the Elite Construction Company handling the Polaku-Sabagia road construction project of the Niger Delta Development commission (Lartey, 2009). Similarly, the quiet community of Tungbo in Sagbama Local Government Council, in Bayelsa State was thrown into confusion of Sunday, July 6, 2009, following the abduction of 74-year-old woman, Lydia Epiidi, by unknown gunmen. Her abduction came barely two days after the visit of the presidential implementation committee on amnesty to the state (Ebri & Etim, 2009).

Cross River State: In Cross River State, kidnappers on Monday, November 9, 2009, kidnapped Mrs. Victoria Ickeke Idiege Omang, second wife of a Cross River State House of Assembly member N100million offer was turned down for her release, as her abductors saw it as an “insult” and further insisted on collecting N150million ransom as earlier demanded (Una, 2009). Also, the kidnapping of an unidentified 15-year-old secondary school girl who was returning from school was another incidence in Cross River State. The kidnappers called on her parents to meet their conditions or risk her life (Inyang, 2009).

Delta State: in Delta State, on December 23, 2008, an 82 — year old pa Jacob Odivwi Edjesa was kidnapped by gunmen at his residence in Emonu-oregun, Ughelli Local Government Area of Delta State. The octogenarian was murdered by his abductors due to slow response by the Nigerian Police Force (Akinrefon, 2008). Also, the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) abducted six foreign crew members from a chemical tanker “Siehern Peace”. This tanker was seized about 20 nautical miles from Escravos on Sunday July 6, 2009. The victims were Captain Yuriy Shastim (Russia), Chief Engineer. Vasvi Bondarkov (Russia), Engineer. Viktor Koshevoy (Russia), Cadet Banjit Singh Dhindsa (India), Arivando Galima and Tavares Rouirgo (Philippines) (Ebri & Etirn, 2009).

Edo State: In Edo State, the worrisome situation started in February, 2009. This was an incidence where a seven-year-old son of the Chairman of Ovia South-west Local Government Council of Edo State, Mr. Monday, Aighoaei was abducted while he was being dropped t school. It was reliably gathered however, that the little boy was set free after ransom was paid to the kidnappers (Egbegbulem, 2009). Few days after this, another kidnapping took place in which the victim unfortunately ended up in the grave. The victim identified as the managing director of “God is Good Motors,” Mr. Edwin Ajaere was kidnapped and found dead few days later, after a ₦100million ransom was paid out of the ₦200million demanded. His death was linked to fear of exposure by his cousin who was a part of the gang. The ugly incident was followed by the kidnap of the wife of Edo State Commissioner for works, Mr. Andrew Bayagbona, who was abducted in her residence in Benin City. A sum of Ni 00million ransom was demanded before her release (Ebegbulem, 2009).

Similarly, General Ademokhia was kidnapped in his farm by suspected Niger Delta militants. An undisclosed ransom was demanded for this release, which he invariably argued for not having such an amount. He spent two days in the hands of his abductors whom he later described as “very nice” people (Ebegbulem, 2009). Also unidentified gunmen abducted a Benin-based transporter, Mr. Monday Osayande, the managing Director of Big Joe Motors in Benin City. Osayande pledged to offer the sum of N15million for his release, but his kidnappers refused, and as well demanded for ₦100million ransom (Osarogiagbon, 2009). Nevertheless, a lecturer of the Federal Polytechnic Auchu was abducted and a ransom of five million naira was demanded by his abductors who are believed to be students of his institution (Inyang, 2009). Again on

Saturday, June 13, 2009, kidnappers abducted a branch manager of alone of the old generation banks on mission road, Benin, Benin City. The seizure of the bank manager came on the heels of the abduction and release of a member of staff of the University of Benin, Mrs. Eremeh, by gunmen. It was learnt that Eramah, a departmental secretary in the School of Dentistry, was abducted while she was taking her children to school on Monday, June 8, 2009.

According to the source, the gunmen who abducted the woman did not take away the children, unlike the members of the gang who abducted a medical doctor and his three children at Auchi. A sum of ₦10million ransom payment was demanded from the husband of Eramah for her release (Nwankwo, Aborisade & Oni, 2009).

Gunmen also kidnapped a former Chairman of the Nigerian Bar Association in Benin, Mr. Solomon Odiase, and the parents of the Chairman of Ovia North-east Local Government Area of Edo State, Mr. Faustian Ovienrioba. Sources claimed that Odiase was abducted on his way to Iwu Ovia North-east L.G.A., on Saturday evening, September 26, 2009, while the parents of the Council Chairman were kidnapped at Emah, on Monday, September 28, 2009 in the morning. No ransom was made for the parents of the Council chairman as at when report was filed in, but in the case of Odiase, ₦100million was demanded for his release (Fabiya, Soriwei & Olatunji, 2009). Also, a veterinary doctor from the Ministry of Agriculture who was meant to represent the Minister of Agriculture, Dr. Sayyadi Ruma, at the annual conference of the pharmaceutical society of Nigeria, was abducted by unknown gunmen. A sum of N20million ransom was demanded from the doctor for his release (Anonymous, 2009; Punch Newspaper, November, 11).

In the first week of June 2024, six South Korean oil workers were kidnapped in Caw throne Channel located near Degema, Bonny and Akukutoru Local Government Areas of Rivers State. In the course of taking these hostages, five military personnel were killed in the raid and two policemen injured. The movement for the Ernancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) claimed responsibility for that attack. These abducted expatriate oil workers were members of staff of shell, their names were given as H.D. Kwom, A. Park, S.B. Kim, O.K. Kim and H.D. Kimi (Dode 2007, cited this view from the editorial of dailysun Newspaper, June 9, 2006).

However, on July 25, 2008, five Russians were abducted by suspected pirates from a marine carrier (Herkules) with registration number 7523192 and call sign, DSAS. The vessel was on chatter by Saipen Nigeria Limited, a subsidiary of EM Group, to their operational field at Akpo oil when it was captured 19 nautical miles from the shores of Bonny. Similarly, 2 hours later, eight expatriates from Global Gas Company, one of the gas servicing companies operating at Bonny Island were abducted by six heavily armed me in the early hours of July 26, 2008. These expatriates included: two Russians, five Latvians and one Lithuanian. The armed men invaded an LPG tanker and shot two civilians before abducting the expatriates (Isine, 2008).

Similarly the Nigerian footballer, Joseph Yobo, had put in a large chunk of his foreign earnings before his elder brother was set free by dare devil kidnappers who had trailed him from a night club to his home in Port Harcourt (Inyang, 2009).

On Tuesday, 8th March 2010, at about 0840 hours, ten-armed men dressed in military camouflage invaded road bridge construction site of Macro Engineering Nig. Ltd at Umuaturu, Etche, shot and killed one Sgt Benedict Ajoji attached to 6 PMF Maiduguri, and kidnapped four expatriates: Mr. Miland (Lebabese), Mr. Farid, Mr. Right and Mr. Raymond (Syrian) to an unknown destination. A ₦50,000,000 ransom was said to have been demanded for their release.

On Sunday, 5th August 2010, at about 0300 hours, some armed men attacked on Dr. Alexander Okopho with Miss Evelyn Gilbert While he was driving his blue colored Pathfinder jeep, along NTA Road, by Mgbuoba Market, shot him and kidnapped the said Miss Gilbert to an unknown destination.

On Monday, 24th January 2011 at about 21:00 hours, one Chidube Godwin Ibeakolam was kidnapped by four-armed men along Mbano Camp Oyigbo to an/unknown destination.

On Saturday, 5th March 2011 at about 22.30 hours, one Miss Stella and Miss Stella Ogbunga were kidnapped by Hoodlums along Rumoulogwu, Rumualogu Port Harcourt.

On Monday 21st March 2011, at about 0025 hours, a gang of three-armed men kidnapped one Benedict Kinaka and Gabriel Marcus, brother of who were members of staff of Rivers State Ministry of Transport While driving along Woji road in Port Harcourt.

On Monday 5th March 2012, at about 07:30 hours, one Miss Ma Kaii a student of the University of Port Harcourt was kidnapped by a gang of armed men operating with a white care at Ogbonda estate along Artillery.

On Thursday 8th March 2012, at about 01:40 hours, one Mrs. Ijeorna Olugu Udeh was kidnapped by armed men together with her ash colored pathfinder Jeep with Reg. no. CQ 408 AAA along NTA road. On Thursday 22 March 2012 at about 20:00 hours, one Mrs. Princess Seikibo and her friend were kidnapped by four-armed men in her Hummer Jeep along Obiri-Ikwerre.

Types of Kidnapping

Kidnapping can be categorized into three (3) major typologies. Walsh and Adrian, (1983) identified types of kidnapping based on the motives behind the incidence. These are

- Politically-motivated Kidnapping
- Economic/commercial kidnapping
- Kidnapping for popularity.
- Hostage Situation
- Miscellaneous Kidnapping
- Kidnapping for Robbery

- Kidnapping for Murder (or other non-sexual assault)
- White Slavery
- Child Stealing
- Ransom Skyjacking
- Romantic Kidnapping
- Classic Ransom
- Kidnapping for rape or sexual assault.

Politically-Motivated Kidnapping: According to Ujumadu (2009), politically motivated kidnapping is the most dangerous type of kidnapping. This is because it encompasses every other type of kidnappings. i.e. the economic/commercial and popularity-seeking kidnappings. Walsh and Adrian (1983) noted that revolutionary groups seeking publicity initiated politically-motivated kidnapping in the late 1960s and early 1970s. They also used this form of kidnapping to seek the release of imprisoned guerrillas from jail in addition to ransom payments. According to them, such incidents, involved the kidnapping of the U.S., German and Swiss Ambassadors in 1969 and 1970 respectively; the cases of Signor Aldo Moro in 1978 and U.S. General Dozier in 1982 are included. Jerome (2009) described these types of kidnappers as political activists who make political demands exchange for the release of their captives.

In Nigeria, the incidence of kidnapping in 2003 and 2009 respectively reflected the political motives behind it, these were the kidnap cases of the former Anambra State Governor, Dr. Chris Ngige in 2002, and that of the father of the former Central Bank Governor, Pa Simeon Soludo (Ujurnadu, 2009). This type of kidnapping as earlier noted has been revenge or cruelty such as the desire to inflict involuntary servitude on the victim, to cause pain and grieve to victims loved ones or to commit some further crime against the victim (Walsh & Adrian, 1983).

Oraetoka (2009) argued that most of the kidnapping in Nigeria, especially in the South- east are politically motivated. Following his report, the South-East leader's summit on kidnapping lends credence to the politically motivated theory of kidnapping in the East. These submit brought to fore, that elites have come to realize that kidnappings and associated crimes in the region were politically motivated, not criminally induced as erroneously thought before now. Oraetoka further acknowledges that, in Anambra, Akwa Iborn, Ondo States and the likes, most of the kidnappings are politically motivated. Those in government are responsible for it. A clear example was the crisis between PDP and Labour Party on June 15, 2009 in Ondo State over the abduction of a commissioner's wife for which N10million was demanded as ransom. Nwosu (2009) added to it that, in Nigeria, especially in the South - East, majority of people kidnapped are politicians. Politicians use kidnapping to settle scores with their political rivals.

Economic/Commercial Kidnapping: As earlier noted, Walsh and Adrian (1983), observed that, the over-whelming i.e. 90% majority of modern kidnapping include criminal gain. The situation in Nigeria belongs to this category. Most of these crimes are committed by criminal gangs seeking to make a fortune by collecting ransoms for, the release of their victims, this type of kidnapping for extortion occurred in the U.S.A in the 1920s and the 1930s. Kidnapping of the U.S. Charles Flyer Limburg baby boy was a clear example of economic/commercial kidnapping. Another form of kidnapping that falls within this category is the abduction and sale of women for prostitution, or concubines.

In Nigeria, this type of kidnapping is what is obtainable today. As earlier noted, the former Inspector General of Police, Sir Mike Okiro analyzed that, most kidnapping in the country are used as a source of raising funds, while over \$200,000 is usually requested as money per head. To him, kidnappers and hostage takers got N15million ransom (about 100million naira) between 2006 and 2009 (Kyrian, 2009) Uwake (2009) observed that this type of kidnapping is prevalent specially in the South-Eastern part of Nigeria and is gradually becoming very popular in the south - south region. Jerome (2009) viewed people who get involved in this type of kidnapping as criminal gangs especially in the Niger Delta region who align with the deploy the cover of militant activities to press home their immediate goals of financial reward. Ujumadu (2009) opined that though there had been cases of economic/commercial type of kidnapping it has reduced drastically and the most dangerous type is the one sponsored by politicians. This fact is prevalent in Anambra State of Nigeria.

Popularity-Seeking Kidnapping: Cases where certain groups of terrorists' kidnaps and make it known to the public, that they are responsible for the act, falls within this category. Walsh and Adrian (1983) identified these crops of kidnappers as revolutionary groups, seeking publicity. They use their prowess to make forceful demands from those in authority. The U.S. German and Swiss Ambassadors who were kidnapped by Brazilian terrorists for the release of imprisoned guerrillas in 1969 and 1970 respectively were a typical example of popularity-seeking kidnapping. These kidnappers, in the cause of agitating for their needs, use hostage-taking to hasten the rapid response to their demands. By this, they make themselves popular. This is the situation in the Niger Delta. The militants most times kidnapped foreign expatriate to ostensibly draw government's attention to their demands and afterward make public that they are the ones responsible for the act. An example of this, is the case of the first incidence of kidnapping in the South-South region of Nigeria where the group, movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND). Kidnapped six oil expatriates to draw government's attention to the plight of the region and thereafter claimed responsibility for the menace (Dode, 2007). These and many more incidents in the region made them popular.

The Nigeria Constitution and Efforts to Curb Kidnapping

In Nigeria, the anti-kidnapping law presently prescribes a penalty of 10years imprisonment for kidnappers; some states have come up with even more stringent laws, ranging from life imprisonment to death penalty. But the assessment of this constitutional provision reflects laxity in the implementation process. Not one reported case of kidnapping has been successfully prosecuted so far to serve as deterrent to others and as well promote the constitutional provision (Ekpe, 2009).

Rivers State was reported to be the first state to pass a law, making kidnapping a capital offence in Nigeria (Akwa, 2009). Since then other states like Abia, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Enugu, Ebonyi and Imo have followed suit, with Ondo State proposing a bill awaiting implementation against the act (Inyang, 2009) Also on subsequent occasions, the National Assembly proposed a bill titled “A bill for an Act of Prohibit Kidnapping, Hostage-Taking, and Prescribes Punishment for its Contravention and other Matters Relating Thereto” (Ogbodo, 2009:6). This event was followed by invitation of the former Minister of Defense, Major Gen. Godwin Abbe and his Interior. Minister Counterpart, Dr. Shettima Mustapha as well as the National Security Adviser, Major Gen. Sarki Muktar, the former Inspector General of Police (IGP), Mr. Mike Okiro, and former Director General of the State Security Services (SSS) Mr Afakriya Gadzama To propose possible ways to tackle kidnapping in the country (Ughebe & Jimoh, 2009).

Despite these steps towards making kidnapping a capital offence that attracts “life imprisonment” and “death penalty”, the Nigerian Bar Association (NBA), has urged the governments to exercise caution in their bid to impose death penalty on anybody convicted of kidnapping, and states which have passed the bill already should abolish it and adopt a middle course in the fight against kidnapping. This is because, any proposal on death penalty as punishment would portray Nigeria as backward and retrogressive in view of the global trend, which favours the abolition of death sentence as witnessed in many countries (Ughebe & Jimoh, 2009).

Some States like Rivers, Akwa Ibom, Cross River, Imo, Enugu, Abia, etc, have sealed down the operational hours of motorcyclists in their state, some have even gone far to stop their operations totally to stem down the spate of kidnapping. Several vehicles have been bought for the security agencies especially the police; their operational facilities have also enhanced with a lot of money pumped into the agency to facilitate their activities against kidnappers (Ujumadi, 2009; Anonymous 2009, Community Pulse Newspaper, October, 2022). The Government in the Rivers State of Nigeria has also set-up a special Anti-kidnapping squad. It was an elite squad that received training in counterterrorism. As their Akwa Ibom counterpart, the team has been specially equipped to enable them combat crime of kidnapping in the state. Large quantities of bullet proof vests and other accessories were provided to make their work safer and more efficient (David, 2009). On several occasions, governments have been pledging fat sum of money for anybody that gives information that leads to the arrest of kidnappers.

The security agencies have also risen to the task. Several security summits, involving the Military, Police and other Para-military agencies are always organized within the Federal and State levels of government to check the menace (Udejah, Njokwu, Nzeagwu, Ogugbuaja & Aliu 2009). One of such meetings was that of the police held on Tuesday, September, 29, 2009. The former Inspector General of Police, Mr. Ogbonna Onovo, summoned all officers of the Nigeria Police Force from the rank of commissioner and above to an emergency meeting, following the rising cases of violent crimes and kidnapping in some parts of the country. Their council meeting came six days after Umaru Musa Yar'Adua, late president of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, pronounced insecurity as the greatest challenge facing his administration (Fabiya, Soriwei & Olatunji, 2009).

Following the upsurge of kidnapping in the Niger Delta, the French Ambassador to Nigeria, Jean Micheal Durnoud, declared his country's readiness to work with the federal government to check insecurity in the region. He also stated that his country was set to activate the ministry assistance provision in the Memorandum of Understanding reached between the two countries. According to him, the Special Forces have the necessary experiences of maneuvering the mangrove areas such as those in the Niger Delta (Ogbodo, 2009).

METHODOLOGY

Baridam, (2001:51) posits that research design is the framework or plan that is used as a guide in collecting and analyzing the data for a study. This study adopted the descriptive research design and requires the quasi-experimental design because the elements of the research interest are not under the researcher's control. Thus, the survey method was adopted because it investigates a chosen proportion of a particular population at a particular point in time.

The population of the study will be generally composed of the total population in the nine (9) state of the Niger delta.

The study population is 400 respondents drawn from nine (9) state in the Niger delta. Comprising adult respondents aged 18 to 70 in six selected states of the Niger delta. The decision was justified since the individuals were best suited to give relevant information on this study subject matter and going by reports, these states were seen as flash points in the Niger delta,

To select samples for this study, the simple random sampling technique, as well as the stratified random sampling technique, was adopted since the population of the study consists of sub-groups; simple random sampling and stratified random sampling becomes necessary here. This ensured that an equal representation and chance is given to each stratum. Thus, this technique ensures an unbiased selection of samples in stratum or sub-groups. In doing this, we will identify and select the following states showing the 2006 population figures;

Rivers 7,476,800

Bayelsa 2,537,400

Delta 5,636,100

Edo 4,777,000
Ondo 5,316,600
Abia .4,143,100.

Total 29,887,000

Thus, this will represent our stratum from which the 400 sample population would be purposively drawn for this study.

The interview method was adopted where respondents could not give direct information on the questionnaire due to the problem of Illiteracy. In this case, tape recorders were put to use and the questions in questionnaire translated into Pidgin English and thereafter administered on those who could not read and write.

At the completion of the data collection, all responses were treated in figure tables. This helped to show briefly the trend of the data and the related variables.

The conventional means of discussion and consultation with experts in the general field of Social Sciences was used to validate our data. Such instruments are to be confirmed through discussion and consultation with experts in the field of Peace and Conflict Studies, Criminology and Security Studies, senior colleagues and others considered as experts in the field of study. From this, we come up with the final product for harmonization of various suggestions and views raised during the constructive stage.

Statistics of kidnap cases in Niger Delta

Year	Number of recorded kidnap cases
2007	4,980
2008	4680
2009	10749
2010	6051
2011	5554
2013	1288
2014	3137
2015	9416
2016	15664
2017	8937
2018	3534
2019	2895
2020	4471
2021	5612
2022	4508
2023	3647

Simple bar chart on number of recorded kidnap cases.

From the above two tables, there is clear evidence that kidnapping cases in niger delta began to rise upward from 2013 with several 25 recorded cases. From 2014 the number increased geometrically to 49 and 73 in 2015. From the analysis of the above tables, it shows that the crime of kidnapping has entrenched its stem in Imo State because of its economic and political advantages which affects tremendously the socio-economic development of the state.

Rivers State: In the first week of June 2006, six South Korean oil workers were kidnapped in Caw throne Channel located near Degema, Bonny and Akukotoru Local Government Areas of Rivers State. While taking these hostages, five military personnel were killed in the raid and two policemen injured. The movement for the Ernancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) claimed responsibility for that attack. These abducted expatriate oil workers were members of staff of

shell, their names were given as H.D. Kwom, A. Park, S.B. Kim, O.K. Kim and H.D. Kimi (Dode 2007, cited this view from the editorial of daily sun Newspaper, June 9, 2006).

However, on July 25, 2008, five Russians were abducted by suspected pirates from a marine carrier (Herkules) with registration number 7523192 and call sign, DSAS. The vessel was on charter by Saipen Nigeria Limited, a subsidiary of EM Group, to their operational field at Akpo oil when it was captured 19 nautical miles from the shores of Bonny. Similarly, 2 hours later, eight expatriates from Global Gas Company, one of the gas servicing companies operating at Bonny Island were abducted by six heavily armed men in the early hours of July 26, 2008. These expatriates included: two Russians, five Latvians and one Lithuanian. The armed men invaded an LPG tanker and shot two civilians before abducting the expatriates (Isine, 2008).

On Monday, 15 of January, 2009 unknown gunmen abducted a renowned author and educationist, Captain Elechi Amadi, at his home in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. He was released the following day with the demand of N300million as ransom (Ebri & Etim, 2009). On separate occasions on Tuesday, February 3, 2009, unidentified gunmen abducted Mrs. Gladys Inietie Daukoro, Wife to the Former Minister of State for Energy, Edmund Daukoro and Dr. Elkaya Igom, commissioner for works and Estate with Rivers state Independent Electoral Commission (RSIEC). The abductors demanded the pull-out of Joint Military Task Force (JTF) from Rivers State and the entire Niger Delta region before their release (Obayuwana & Etim, 2009). Meanwhile Ebiri and Etim (2009) report that, before these incident no fewer than five persons were kidnapped in Rivers State. One of these people was a senior official of Agip Oil Company, Mr. Charles W. James, whose abductors demanded a sum of five million naira for his release. Similarly, the Nigerian footballer, Joseph Yobo, had put in a large chunk of his foreign earnings before his elder brother was set free by dare devil kidnappers who had trailed him from a night club to his home in Port Harcourt (Inyang, 2009).

On Friday 2 December 2011, at about 07:30 hours, a gang of armed men kidnapped one Mr. G.S.C. Onyeche, a Director in the Rivers State Ministry of Information, along Okra Market Road, Oyigbo to an unknown destination.

On Thursday 12th January 2012, at about 02: 08 hours, a gang of eight-armed men invaded the residence of one Mr. Agolia Aboko, Vice Chairman, PDP, Rivers State at Rukpakulushi New Layout, robbed him of his valuables and kidnapped his 13-year-old child, Isaac Aboko and fled to an unknown destination.

On Wednesday 18 January 2012, at about 21:30 hours, a gang of hoodlums kidnapped one Pastor. Peter Abanimi along Igbo-Etche road, Umuebulu. His vehicle was abandoned at the scene of the crime and was later recovered by men of the Nigeria police.

CONCLUSION

Nowadays, people are kidnapped on a daily basis for various reasons, such as economic, political, and personal differences. Some of the victims are killed or maimed. The article calls for the government at various levels to intensify awareness campaigns on the evils as well as punishment for kidnapping. Additionally, the enabling laws on kidnapping should be increased. The punishment for kidnapping should be as grave as that for murder and other felonious offences to further instill fear in would-be kidnapers. Finally, citizens should be encouraged to report any suspected incidence or kidnap attempt to security agencies without delay. On the other hand, more security personnel should be deployed to the various communities in the Niger Delta with better arms.

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